

THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: this article describes the timing of speech development and its stages. at each of these stages, the essence of the speech development of preschool children is revealed.

Keywords: children's speech, onto linguistics, "vertical" approach, "horizontal" approach, observation, experiment.

INTRODUCTION

psyche, all activities, therefore, speech development of children is given an important role in the pedagogical process of preschool institutions.

The theoretical study of the research Modern and full-fledged mastery of speech is the first most important condition for the formation of a full-fledged psyche in a child and its further correct development. Modern means started from the very first days after the birth of a child. Full mastery of speech means sufficient volume of language material. Encouraging the child to master speech, to the full extent of his capabilities at every age stage. Attention to the development of a child's coherent speech at the first age stages is especially important because, at this time, the child's brain is growing intensively, and its functions are being formed. Physiologists know that the functions of the central nervous system are easy to train during their natural formation. Without training, the development of these functions is delayed and may even stop forever. The child's speech performs three functions of communication with the outside world: communicative,

cognitive, regulatory.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The term "children's speech" has different meanings. First of all, it is a set of features of the child's speech, due to age and level of intellectual development. The features of children's speech can be sound (the specifics of pronunciation of certain sounds and their combinations), grammatical (the specifics of the use of grammatical constructions, children's innovations, etc.) and semantic (the specifics of the selection and use of words, mastering concepts). Secondly, children's speech is a science that studies the process of children's assimilation of their native language. The scientific discipline that studies the process of assimilation of the native language by children is called linguistics of children's speech, or onto linguistics.

Onto linguistics studies on questions:

- how is the mastery of specific speech skills -pronouncatory, lexical, word-formation, grammatical.
- what features characterize the speech skill of children at different age levels,
- how to see the process of speech formation in perspective?

Identifies two approaches to the study of linguistic phenomena in the child's speech. The first is the so-called "vertical" approach: it is based on looking at the child's speech "from above" from the standpoint of the adult language system, on comparing the units and categories of children's speech with the units and categories of adult language. This makes it possible to differentiate the correct and erroneous in the child's speech, to highlight speech innovations. The second approach is conventionally called "horizontal". The children's language system is

considered as an autonomous object to a certain extent, in which the meanings of many words are specific, the rules for the formation of word forms are simpler than in the "adult" language, etc. The speech development of a child can be represented as a gradual change in temporary language systems, each of which reflects the child's own, also temporary cognitive system. Researchers recognize that only the integration of both approaches will allow us to fully study the phenomenon of children's speech. The most common methods of studying children's speech are natural (observation) and experiment.

Observation - deliberate, purposeful and systematic perception of a child's speech, as a rule, is long. The results of observation are recorded in diaries (most often parental ones), as well as with the help of modern digital media. Diaries of observations of the child 's speech development show the sequence of mastering certain means of language and are of two types:

a) diaries of a general type reflecting the child's assimilation of all structural levels of the language system (phonetic, lexico-semantic, morphemic and syntactic);

b) diaries of selective fixation, in which the development of any one component of the language ability is characterized (for example, the development of sound pronunciation).

c) onto linguistics also uses some types of psycholinguistic experiment:

Associative experiment. It is used to study the child's understanding of the meanings of words and their connections with each other. The child responds to the word - stimulus, named by an adult, with the first word that came to mind, the word-reaction. (The experiment is carried out in the form of a game, during which an adult, naming words, throws a ball to a child or rolls a typewriter, and he quickly performs the same action with respect to an adult and calls his word: album - draw, branch - candy).

The method of interpreting words - allows you to see the peculiarities of

understanding the meanings of words by its speakers. (Tail. It is attached to the animals from behind. For example, the cow ends, and he begins).

The method of addition, which consists in the fact that the child is asked to restore the text in which individual words are omitted. This technique allows us to trace the mechanisms of generation of a coherent text.

Classification methodology - the child classifies the proposed language material. For example, a child is asked to put aside drawings depicting creatures that fly (swim, run); find "superfluous" among three or four images (for example, three animals and one bird), etc. This technique shows how the child performs the operation of highlighting the essential features of the object, as well as the operations of generalization, analysis and synthesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Today, methods of computer processing and fixation of children's texts are widely used (for example, the CHILDES program).

The results obtained in the course of experimental studies do not always make sense to correlate with the age of a particular child, because each person has an individual path to his native language. It is more important to pay attention to the sequence of appearance of certain features that characterize the process of language acquisition.

Currently, there are at least three areas of onto linguistic research:

- 1) the study of the development of the native language by a particular child;
- 2) study of the general patterns of assimilation of the native language by different children;
- 3) identification of common patterns of assimilation of different languages by different children.

All three directions are directly connected, the decision of each of the subsequent ones is somehow based on the decision of the previous ones.

CONCLUSION

The development of speech is one of the most important acquisitions of a child in preschool childhood and is considered in modern preschool education as a common basis for the upbringing and education of children. Studies of Russian psychologists and teachers have proved that mastering speech does not just add something to the development of a child, but rebuilds his entire problem and the results of the pedagogical experiment confirmed the correctness of the hypothesis put forward and allowed us to formulate the following conclusion: the purposeful and systematic use of fiction in working with children of younger preschool age contributes to the most effective development of their coherent speech, which confirms the hypothesis of the work.

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